

Joint Resource Allocation and Link Adaptation for Beyond 5G Time Sensitive Communications

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Abstract—Integrating 5G and Beyond networks with Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) is essential for meeting the stringent Time Sensitive Communications (TSC) requirements of Industry 4.0 applications. Configured Grant (CG) scheduling is a promising technique for reducing uplink latency and providing deterministic traffic service. However, CG scheduling faces severe challenges from the use of semi-static Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCS) and potential Resource Blocks (RBs) collisions among multiple TSN traffic flows, due to its pre-configured resource allocation. To confront these challenges, this paper introduces an enhanced CG scheduling scheme that integrates link adaptation with proactive collision detection and resolution. The presented approach involves dynamically adjusting the MCS based on current channel conditions and dealing with RB collisions through proactive monitoring and dynamic scheduling. Simulation results demonstrate significant improvements in transmission reliability and reduced Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) failures, making it a viable solution for 5G and beyond networks integrating TSN in the Radio Access Network (RAN).

Index Terms—Beyond 5G; URLLC; Configured Grant; Scheduling; Resource Allocation; Link Adaptation; Collision Resolution

I. INTRODUCTION

As the deployment of 5G networks continues to expand, the focus intensifies on ensuring ultra-reliable and low-latency communications (URLLC), critical for next-generation applications such as automated industrial systems, thereby setting the stage for advancements into 5G and Beyond [1]. The critical demands of URLLC require innovative solutions for efficient network resource management. The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has introduced several mechanisms across its Releases, mostly at the PHY and MAC layers, to support these requirements [2].

Despite the advancements URLLC brings in terms of latency and reliability, it alone is insufficient for applications requiring strict timing guarantees and deterministic performance [3]. To address these challenges, the integration of 5G with Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) is crucial for supporting the communication demands of Industry 4.0 applications [4]. Recently, 3GPP standards with the goal of achieving deterministic URLLC [5] have introduced time-sensitive communications (TSC) [6]. In the proposed architecture [7], the 5G network acts as a logical bridge between TSN devices aiming to serve wirelessly the deterministic traffic needs.

A key enabler of TSC in 5G systems is implementing the TSC Assistance Information (TSCAI) within Radio Access

Network (RAN) [8]. TSCAI provides details about the TSC traffic flow, such as the periodicity, flow direction (uplink or downlink) of the traffic, and time-offset. This information can be used by the gNB to decide the optimal allocation of radio resources. By aligning resource allocation with the specific characteristics of TSC traffic, the gNB can ensure that data packets are transmitted within the required time constraints [9].

One major challenge to supporting TSN traffic in a 5G network is the need for precise coordination between TSN and 5G scheduling mechanisms. The integration must ensure that the deterministic nature of TSN is preserved while taking advantage of the flexibility of the 5G scheduler. Configured Scheduling (CS), which can be categorized as Configured Grant (CG) in uplink and Semi-Persistent Scheduling (SPS) in downlink, offers a more stable and predictable resource allocation [10]. CG promises to reduce the latency of uplink data transmission by allowing devices to operate on a semi-static scheduling basis, thus making no use of Scheduling Requests (SRs). By pre-allocating uplink resources, CG enables devices to transmit data as soon as they become available, bypassing the traditional process of dynamic grant acquisition from the network. This makes CG a promising option to support TSC [11].

CS can struggle particularly in scenarios of varying channel conditions. Specifically, fading and path loss could lead to failed initial transmissions which are typically solved with Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) retransmissions. However, this policy introduces delays that are unacceptable for TSC traffic flows. In contrast to grant-based scheduling, where link adaptation is performed on a slot basis, in CS the modulation and coding scheme (MCS) is assigned in a static way, and thus, it is not able to mirror the changes in the wireless channel in a same manner. As a result, transmission under CS is more likely to lead to retransmissions. The support of multiple CG and SPS configurations, where each may be assigned a different MCS [12], can partially solve the issue of semi-static MCS. The gNB can dictate through dedicated signaling which to use depending on the channel measured. Nevertheless, the MCS values remain statically assigned and might not accurately reflect the channel conditions. To solve this, authors in [13], present an enhanced method that dynamically adjusts the MCS for downlink 5G TSC, leading to an SPS scheme which is more robust to channel variations and can support more TSC traffic flows.

However, their solution is limited to the downlink. Another potential challenge for CS in serving TSC traffic flows comes from the degradation caused by resource allocation conflicts among traffic flows with different periodicities. In [14], the authors address the problem of possible conflicts between different periodicities traffic flows by proposing a novel scheduling scheme that configures multiple grants for each TSN flow, thereby avoiding overlap and improving the overall number of satisfactorily served TSN flows. Although their solution resolves potential conflicts, the MCS is considered semi-static and thus not taking into account potential failures of initial transmissions and impact to the TSC latency requirements.

To address these limitations and extend the benefits of link adaptation to the CG, this paper proposes an enhanced CG scheduling scheme that integrates dynamic MCS adjustment with the resolution of potential Resource Blocks (RBs) collisions due to the overlap of TSC traffic flow periodicities. Specifically, to achieve this, a combination of proactive monitoring and resource allocation is used to resolve potential collisions. By taking advantage of the link adaptation that dynamic grant assignment offers, the goal is to adjust the CG to accommodate varying channel conditions.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II provides the system model and problem description. Section III details the proposed Joint Resource allocation and Link Adaptation. Section IV presents the performance evaluation of the proposed scheme. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and discusses possible future work.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

A. System Model

The system model of this study consists of a single gNB serving multiple CG-capable UEs. Resources are assigned to UEs in a time-frequency Resource Grid. In time domain, the grid is divided in Transmission Time Intervals (TTIs) each consisting of 14 orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) symbols. In frequency domain, the grid is split in RBs. It is considered that all UEs use the available 14 symbols for transmission in the time domain and M number of consecutive RBs in the frequency domain. In order to enable CS the gNB assigns each UE with a CG configuration using Radio Resource Control (RRC) message. More specifically, during *RRCReconfiguration* message, the *ConfiguredGrantConfig* Information Element (IE) informs the UEs of the CG assigned to them. Each UE generates a traffic flow F_i , for which the gNB is informed by the TSCAI regarding its key characteristics, such as the periodicity of packet generation and the traffic payload. Based on this information, the gNB constructs the CG configuration for each UE, which consists of the following fields:

- **Periodicity (P_i):** Represents the interval at which the i th UE transmits data packets.
- **Frequency Domain Resource Assignment (FDRA $_i$):** A bitmap string that results in a contiguous RB interval $\{RB_{start_i}, RB_{end_i}\}$ allocated to the UE, where the total number of RBs is M . It is considered, that UEs may

receive overlapping RBs as long as they have different P_i . This allows the system to efficiently reuse RBs and maximize the available bandwidth.

- **Modulation and Coding Scheme and Transport Block Size ($mcsAndTBS_i$):** an integer which indicates a row in the MCS table, to extract the modulation and Transport Block Size (TBS) used for transmission [15]. From now on we refer to this field as mcs_i .
- **Time Domain Resource Assignment (TDRA $_i$):** Defines the time slot offset and the time domain allocation for the transmission. It is implied that all served UEs have the same time slot offset and time domain allocation, using all 14 symbols for transmission.

Fig. 1: Illustration of the CG scheduling scheme.

These parameters $\{P_i, FDRA_i, TDRA_i, mcs_i\}$ together form the CG configuration for each UE, denoted as CG_i . In Figure 1 a CG configuration applied to the Resource Grid can be viewed.

Normally, in dynamic scheduling the $mcsAndTBS$ is decided to preserve a target Block Error Rate (BLER) and the choice depends on the uplink Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) measurements. Then based on the decided $mcsAndTBS$ and the traffic payload that needs to be served, the allocated resources are assigned. However, in CS, the gNB does not have Channel State Information (CSI) when initially constructing the configuration. The assumption that all UEs use the full time slot simplifies the resource allocation to determining the number of Resource Blocks (RBs), M , based on the initial MCS choice mcs_i .

Upon reception of the CG configuration, each UE i transmits its traffic packets to the gNB when the slot matches the received periodicity, calculating each time the HARQ process number h_i .

In case re-transmissions are needed, the reactive-CG scheme has been implemented, where the gNB dictates the UE to re-transmit with a Downlink Control Information (DCI) containing an uplink grant.

B. Problem Description

The allocation of periodic resources to TSC traffic in 5G networks poses significant challenges, as discussed above,

particularly when different TSC flows have varying periodicities. As firstly described in [14], the potential share of RBs may lead to collisions if not properly managed. If time domain offset is considered the same for all UEs, then these collisions occur at the least common multiple (LCM) of the periodicities of the traffic flows involved, if there are resource blocks RBs in common between the overlapping UEs as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Illustration of Multiple TSC Traffic Collision Problem as described in [14]

To solve the performance degradation that comes if these collisions are not properly handled, we propose an alternative method where collisions are resolved through a combination of detection and dynamic scheduling. Furthermore, the proposed scheme, takes advantage of the signaling used to resolve the collisions to also apply link adaptation to the CG transmission. By implementing this joint resource allocation and link adaptation mechanism, we aim to enhance the reliability and efficiency of CG scheduling.

III. JOINT RESOURCE ALLOCATION AND LINK ADAPTATION

In the proposed scheme, the gNB firstly checks for collisions between different CG UEs every TTI. Upon detecting that the K UEs will collide due to overlap in their resources, it dynamically schedules $K - 1$ of them using grant based approach. In order to prevent transmission interference, this technique temporarily reallocates the $K - 1$ UEs to new, collision-free RBs. The gNB then sends new uplink grants to the rescheduled UEs to inform them about the new RBs to use and updated MCS value if necessary. The UE not chosen for dynamic scheduling will keep the CG configuration for transmission.

On the UE side, upon receiving a dynamic scheduling grant, the CG is overridden, and the dynamic grant is used for the transmission of the pending traffic. Following this, the CG configuration is changed to $CG_{i,updated}$, reflecting the new MCS in the mcs_i value. Additionally $FDRA_i$ is adjusted with the RB allocation coming from the dynamic grant. This modification ensures that the CG configuration better reflects the current channel conditions, as the MCS was calculated based on a more recent assessment. For better

resource utilization, we do not keep the RBs of the dynamic grant permanently. Instead, based on CG_i , we regulate RB_{start} and RB_{end} to support the traffic needs according to the new MCS. The same update is done in the gNB so they both use the $CG_{i,updated}$. Next time the i th UE transmits using CG, it will use the new $CG_{i,updated}$, until it receives some new grant to override it again. Figure 3 shows the described proposed mechanism.

Fig. 3: Proposed Scheme to resolve collisions

It should be noted that, unlike traditional dynamic scheduling, this scheme does not require an SR. The gNB knows that the UE will need to be served at the periodic intervals its traffic is generated.

This Joint Resource Allocation and Link Adaptation process consists of the following key steps:

- 1) **Determine Colliding UEs:** Identify the UEs involved in the collision.
- 2) **Prioritize UEs:** Choose the UEs to be proactively rescheduled.
- 3) **Allocate Dynamic Grants:** Assign new resource blocks and MCS to the selected $K - 1$ UEs. When changing the MCS, the RBs should be carefully selected to ensure the new resources can still accommodate the UE's traffic volume.
- 4) **Update CG Configuration:** After the dynamic grant is received use it to transmit the data. Then, update the CG configuration with the new MCS and RBs, ensuring that future transmissions are better adapted to the channel conditions.

Deciding which UEs will receive dynamic grants and which will retain the CG in the occasion of a collision must be done carefully, as it affects network performance and resource utilization. For this reason, a selection algorithm is designed to determine the UEs to receive a grant based on their periodicities and historical grant allocations. Integrated in the gNB's scheduler the proposed algorithm aims to balance immediate transmission requirements and long-term fairness. Prioritizing UEs based on their periodicities is vital for the effectiveness of this selection algorithm. Specifically:

- **Lower Periodicity UEs:** UEs with lower periodicities transmit more frequently, and as a result a suboptimal MCS will impact a larger number of their transmissions,

leading to a higher likelihood of retransmissions. By prioritizing these UEs for dynamic grants, we make sure they benefit from the most up-to-date MCS, improving their transmission efficiency and reducing the chances of retransmission.

- **Higher Periodicity UEs:** UEs with higher periodicities transmit less frequently and might be more impacted by using an outdated MCS. Prioritizing those, can help their traffic to be successfully transmitted on the first attempt.

The proposed algorithm incorporates these considerations into a simple linear objective function that combines the periodicity of each UE with their historical grant allocations. The objective function is defined as follows:

$$O_i = \alpha \cdot \left(\frac{1}{P_i}\right) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot P_i - \beta \cdot H_i \quad (1)$$

where:

- O_i is the objective value for UE i ,
- P_i is the periodicity of UE i ,
- α is a weight parameter that adjusts the importance of prioritizing lower vs higher periodicities,
- β is a weight parameter that adjusts the importance of fairness so that not the same UEs are chosen constantly,
- H_i is the historical count of grants allocated to UE i .

The basics steps of the algorithm can be seen in Algorithm 1.

To find the optimal balance between overall system and individual performance we aim to find the best choice of the parameters α and β . These optimal choice depends on the specific set-up, both on the periodicities involved but also on the channel parameters. Having these in mind, we define a composite objective function, $J(\alpha, \beta)$, to evaluate the performance of different parameter combinations. This can be given as:

$$J(\alpha, \beta) = \text{CRC}_{\text{total}}(\alpha, \beta) + \max(\text{CRC}_i(\alpha, \beta)) \quad (2)$$

where:

- $\text{CRC}_{\text{total}}(\alpha, \beta)$ represents the total Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) failures, across all UEs for given α and β .
- $\max(\text{CRC}_i(\alpha, \beta))$ is the maximum CRC failures percentage observed among all UEs for given α and β .

The optimization problem can be stated as:

$$\min_{\alpha, \beta} J(\alpha, \beta) \quad (3)$$

subject to:

$$0 \leq \alpha \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

$$0 \leq \beta \leq 1 \quad (5)$$

To solve the optimization problem for a given set up of UEs, we follow the following steps:

- 1) **Run Multiple Simulations:** For each combination of α and β , run multiple simulations to gather data on total CRC failures and per-UE CRC failures.

- 2) **Calculate Metrics:** Compute the mean total CRC failures and the mean maximum CRC failures among UEs for each combination.
- 3) **Evaluate Composite Objective:** Calculate the composite objective value $J(\alpha, \beta)$ for each pair of α and β .
- 4) **Identify Optimal Parameters:** Find the values of α and β that minimize the composite objective function.

Algorithm 1 Selection Algorithm for Dynamic Grant Allocation

- 1: Initialize historical grants: $H_i = 0 \quad \forall UE_i \in \text{colliding_ues}$
 - 2: Calculate objective values:
 - 3: **for** each $UE_i \in \text{colliding_ues}$ **do**
 - 4: $O_i \leftarrow \alpha \cdot \left(\frac{1}{P_i}\right) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot P_i - \beta \cdot H_i$
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: Sort UEs by O_i and select top $K - 1$:
selected_ues $\leftarrow \text{sort}(\text{colliding_ues}, \text{by } O_i)[1 : K - 1]$
 - 7: Update historical grants for each $UE_i \in \text{selected_ues}$:
 $H_i \leftarrow H_i + 1$
 - 8: **return** selected_ues
-

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Experimental Set up

The simulations conducted in this study are based on the srsRAN platform [16], a highly configurable open source software suite for 4G and 5G mobile networks. Specifically, we utilize the srsRAN gNB app as the base station and the srsRAN UE app to model multiple CG-UEs. To support multiple UE connection GNU Radio environment is used, with the support of ZeroMQ (ZMQ) [17]. This setup enables efficient communication between the gNB and multiple UEs by handling both downlink and uplink signal samples through a centralized broker.

The channel conditions in the simulation are modeled using a small-scale fading model to capture the rapid fluctuations in signal amplitude and phase due to multi-path propagation. Specifically, the channel fading is simulated using the small-fading part of the mode described in [18].

The small-scale channel fading coefficient h evolves according to:

$$h(t + 1) = \rho h(t) + \eta(t)$$

where $\eta(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1 - \rho^2)$ and ρ is the channel correlation coefficient. This model captures the temporal correlation of the small-scale fading, making it suitable for simulating realistic industrial wireless communication scenarios. The parameters used in the simulation are listed in Table I:

Parameter	Value
Number of UEs	3
UE periodicities	{8 ms, 5 ms, 10 ms}
β	Optimized (varied from 0 to 1)
α	Optimized (varied from 0 to 1)
ρ	0.8

TABLE I: Simulation setup parameters

B. Experimental Results

To assess the performance of the proposed dynamic collision resolution mechanism, we compare it with two benchmark schemes:

- **Lower Periodicities First:** This scheme prioritizes UEs with lower periodicities for dynamic grant allocation. So when UEs are expected to collide, it will always select, among the ones involved, those with lower periodicities. It can be seen as a special case of Algorithm1 for $\alpha = 0$ and $\beta = 0$.
- **Higher Periodicities First:** This scheme prioritizes UEs with higher periodicities. This can also be viewed as a special case of Algorithm1, for $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 0$.

Additionally, the dedicated resource allocation scheme, where each UE has dedicated resources and as a result experiences no collisions, is used for comparison.

Fig. 4: Percentage of CRC failures on initial transmission for different schemes: dedicated resources, lower periodicities priority, higher periodicities priority, and the proposed algorithm.

As shown in Figure 4, the percentage of CRC failures on initial transmission varies across different schemes. The dedicated resource allocation scheme eliminates collisions but may not optimally adapt to channel variations, resulting in consistent CRC failure rates across all UEs. The lower periodicities priority scheme shows improved performance for frequently transmitting UEs, while the higher periodicities one considers less frequently transmitting UEs to mitigate the impact of sub-optimal MCS settings. The proposed algorithm balances these aspects by dynamically adjusting to current channel conditions and historical transmission success.

By comparing these results, we can see the trade-offs between different prioritization schemes and the effectiveness of the proposed dynamic collision resolution mechanism in balancing fairness and performance.

While the proposed dynamic collision resolution mechanism offers improvements in performance, it introduces additional signaling overhead. This overhead comes from the need to dynamically schedule and allocate resources, which requires additional control signaling between the gNB and the UEs. The trade-off between improved reliability and

increased signaling overhead is an important consideration in the design and implementation of this mechanism. In the fixed MCS allocation scheme with dedicated resources assigned to each UE, the signaling overhead comes from the need of re-transmissions and depends on how optimistic the assigned MCS is to the wireless channel. Figure 5 shows that the signaling overhead introduced by means of Physical Downlink Control Channel (PDCCH) transmissions of the proposed scheme, compared to fixed MCS CG for different fading channel characteristics.

Fig. 5: UL PDCCH transmissions vs. Channel correlation coefficient ρ

As it can be seen, the proposed scheme with the constant re-scheduling of UEs introduces some signalling overhead compared to the fixed CG allocation in dedicated resources. However, as the channel experiences greater variations across time, which can be adjusted from the channel correlation coefficient ρ , the difference in the number of UL PDCCH transmissions required becomes smaller. The last observation favors the proposed scheme since it also offers the advantages already presented.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we introduced an enhanced CG scheduling scheme aimed at improving resource utilization and meeting the stringent requirements of TSCs. By integrating link adaptation and proactive collision detection, our approach addresses the limitations of semi-static MCS and the challenges of resource block collisions. The simulation results demonstrated that the proposed scheme significantly reduces CRC failures and improves overall transmission reliability, and at the same time, latency since re-transmissions are decreased. It is also shown that the gains are influenced by the selection algorithm's ability to balance fairness and overall system performance. However, these improvements come at the cost of increased signaling overhead caused by the additional PDCCH transmissions needed. It is noteworthy, that the added overhead is lesser when channel conditions deteriorate. Future work will explore optimizing the fairness parameters and improving the dynamic scheduling algorithms for further performance gains. Additionally, the comparison

with other CG schemes, like the K-repetition, will be investigated to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the presented method.

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